

CORPORATE GOVERNANCE AND CAPITAL STRUCTURE: EVIDENCE FROM NIGERIA LISTED NON-FINANCIAL SERVICES FIRMS

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Abstract

Purpose – This study examines the link between corporate governance using board size, outside directors, ownership concentration, managerial ownership, director remuneration, and CEO duality, and capital structure based on total debt ratio and the long-term debt ratio of Nigeria listed non-financial services firms.

Design/methodology/approach – A multiple regression analysis was used to estimate the relationship between corporate governance and capital structure during 2012-2021.

Findings – The results suggest that board size, non-executive directors, and ownership concentration are positively related to total debt ratio and long-term debt ratio, whereas director remuneration is negatively related. Managerial ownership is negatively related to long-term debt ratio. CEO duality is found to be insignificant. Control variables such as profitability and liquidity are negatively related to total debt ratio and long-term debt ratio, whereas firm size is positively related. Asset tangibility is positively related to long-term debt ratio and negatively related to total debt ratio.

Practical implications – The results provide support to corporate managers in establishing an optimal capital structure, and to regulators for enacting laws and developing institutional support to make corporate governance mechanisms work more effectively in Nigeria.

Originality/value – The results contribute to the literature by illuminating the significant links between corporate governance and capital structure of listed non-financial services firms in Nigeria. Note, however, the results are useful to listed non-financial services companies in Nigeria.

Keywords Capital Structure, Corporate Governance, Listed Non-Financial Firms, Nigerian Exchange Group.

Paper type Research paper

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1. Introduction

The capital structure or mix of firms listed in Nigeria calls for concern due to very high debt component. In a study by Yahaya and Andow (2015), debt capital also known as financial leverage, of firms operating in Nigeria averages 68 percent, some are as high as 88 percent. These figures are too high and undesirable. Businesses need to have environments friendly to accessing capital through the debt market because it is presumably cheap. However, due largely to political and socioeconomic instabilities in Nigeria, debt capital cost is very high and by extension, weighted average cost of capital is very high too. In addition, there are limited empirical studies in Nigeria that link corporate governance with capital structure. Some of the few studies available either cover short-term periods or look at the listed deposit money banks only. Some others use few variables, with limited usefulness. It is in view of these problems that the paper seeks for the intervention of corporate governance mechanisms as solutions to help reduce the high debt component of corporate capital structure among listed non-financial services companies in Nigeria. Corporate governance focuses on the ways by which suppliers of capital to firms assure themselves of getting returns on their investment (Shleifer & Vishny, 1997). Sound corporate governance practices are essential for sustainable development and growth of an economy. In particular, the countries that have implemented sound corporate governance practices generally experienced a vigorous growth of corporate sector, and grasp more ability in attracting capital to lubricate the economy.

Also, good governance augment the performance of a company not only by establishing and maintaining a corporate culture that motivates the management to take those actions that maximize the shareholder's wealth but also by reducing the cost of funds. A great deal of empirical research to analyze the influence of corporate governance on capital structure has been carried out in developed countries (see, e.g. Anderson et al., 2004; Berger et al., 1997; Fosberg, 2004; Friend and Lang, 1988; Mehran, 1992); whereas, little is known about the developing countries that have different institutional structures (see, e.g. Abor, 2007; Bokpin and Arko, 2009; Kyereboah-Coleman and Biekpe, 2006; Wen et al., 2002). In particular, empirical research to estimate the impact of some corporate governance attributes such as board size, outside directors, ownership concentration, managerial ownership, director remuneration, and CEO duality etc., on capital choices of Nigeria firms is very much limited. Thus, a diminutive research in this area has evoked the need for this study. Furthermore, this study attempts to fill a gap in the literature by illuminating the significant links between corporate governance and capital structure of firms in Nigeria. The rest of the paper proceeds as follows. The following section presents a brief background of corporate governance in Nigeria, and the measures of corporate governance and their relation to capital structure. The subsequent section presents research methodology, results, and discussion on empirical findings. Finally, the paper ends up with conclusions.

Nigeria has weak corporate governance mechanisms compared to companies in developed countries. The government of Nigeria has taken various steps to improve the corporate governance, particularly after opening the secondary market for foreign investors on an equal basis with the local investors. The most important initiative in this connection was the establishment of the Nigeria Securities and Exchange Commission (NSEC), with the aims to develop a modern and efficient corporate sector, and a capital market based on sound regulatory principles to promote economic growth. NSEC introduced the Code of Corporate Governance (CCG) in 2008 in order to establish a system whereby a company is directed and controlled by its directors in compliance with the best practices so as to safeguard the interests of diversified stakeholders. The CCG is based on internationally recognized principles and lay emphasis on openness, transparency, and accountability in the affairs of listed companies. Moreover, it requires directors to discharge their fiduciary responsibilities diligently in the larger interests of all stakeholders. In summary, included in CCG relevant to board size, outside directors, qualification of directors, CEO duality, functions of board of directors, and financial reporting framework etc., is to enhance accountability and efficiency as well as to optimize the interests of a broader group of stakeholders.

2. Literature Review

A number of empirical studies have shown that corporate governance attributes have influence on the financing decisions of firms (Abor, 2007; Anderson et al., 2004; Berger et al., 1997; Bokpin & Arko, 2009; Fosberg, 2004; Friend & Lang, 1988; Kyereboah-Coleman & Biekpe, 2006; Mehran, 1992; Wen et al., 2002; Wiwattanakantang, 1999).

2.1 Board size

An effective board is essential to the success of a company. The board being the highest decision making body in a company has the responsibility to provide superior strategic guidance to ensure the firm's growth and maximize the return to investors. Moreover, board is charged with monitoring and disciplining the senior management. According to Adams and Mehran (2003) a bigger board can effectively monitor the actions of management and provides better expertise. Conversely, Lipton and Lorsch (1992) argue that large boards are less effective compared to small boards because some directors may free-ride on the efforts of others. Existing literature relevant to board size and capital structure yields mixed findings. Berger et al. (1997) found a significant and negative correlation between board size and leverage. Wiwattanakantang (1999) found that board size is negatively related with leverage but the relationship is statistically insignificant. Anderson et al. (2004) found a negative relationship between board size and the cost of debt financing. Moreover, they showed that an additional board member is associated with about a 10 basis point lower cost of debt financing. Thus, this finding suggests that large boards adopt high debt policy to raise the value of the firm. Abor (2007)

and Bokpin and Arko (2009) reported a significant positive relationship between board size and capital structure for Ghanaian firms. Kyereboah-Coleman and Biekpe (2006) have shown a significant and positive association between board size and the total debt ratio and the short-term debt ratio. Finally, Wen et al. (2002) found a positive relationship between board size and leverage but the relationship is statistically insignificant.

2.2 Non-executive directors

Non-executive directors also known as outside directors on the boards are desirable because of their knowledge, broad vision, and independence from management. A high degree of board independence enables non-executive directors to monitor the actions of the management more closely and take appropriate governance actions, which may even involve the dismissals of some of the top managers. According to Weisbach (1988), top managers face more vigorous monitoring when the board of directors is controlled by independent or outside directors. According to Pfeffer (1972), board size and composition are not random or independent factors, but are, rather, rational organizational responses to the conditions of the external environment. For instance, firms with greater needs for access to the capital market would be expected to have greater percentage of outside directors on their boards. Evidence concerning the relationship between board composition and leverage yields mixed findings. Berger et al. (1997) have shown that leverage is significantly lower when a firm has lower fraction of outside directors. Wen et al. (2002) reported a significant and negative relationship between board composition and leverage suggesting that managers seek lower leverage when they face stronger corporate governance. Alternatively, Pfeffer (1972) reported a significant positive relationship between the proportion of board members representing financial institutions and debt-equity ratio. Anderson et al. (2004) found a negative association between board independence and costs of debt. Moreover, they showed that debt costs are 17.5 basis points lower for firms with boards dominated by independent directors relative to firms with insider-stacked boards which suggest that bondholders view board independence as an important element in the pricing of the firm's debt. Abor (2007) found a positive relationship between leverage and outside directors. Bokpin and Arko (2009) reported a positive but statistically insignificant relationship between board independence and the debt ratio. Kyereboah-Coleman and Biekpe (2006) have shown that long-term leverage and total leverage are positively related with the proportion of outside directors in the board but the relationship is statistically insignificant. Mehran (1992) reported a positive but statistically insignificant relationship between the percentage of investment bankers on the firm's board and the long-term debt ratio.

2.3 Ownership concentration

The ownership of blockholders may help to mitigate the agency problems between managers and shareholders. In general, blockholders have more ability than dispersed shareholders to influence the management's decisions. For instance, blockholders may force to the management to take those actions that maximize the shareholder's

wealth. They may demand higher debt levels due to low cost compared to new equity issue. Apart from tax shields considerations, blockholders may force management to use more debt because it reduces the management's discretionary control over the firm's cash flow, and stop them to engage resources in inefficient activities. Although the use of debt may also increase the bankruptcy risk but investors who owned a well-diversified portfolio of investments can manage the risk.

Friend and Lang (1988) argued that firms with major shareholders tend to have higher debt ratio than those with no major shareholders. These explanations suggest a positive association between blockholders share ownership and leverage. Brailsford et al. (2002) have shown a statistically significant and positive relationship between shares owned by external blockholders and leverage. Fosberg (2004) found that the amount of debt in a firm's capital structure is directly related to the proportion of shares held by the blockholders but inversely related to the number of blockholders a firm has. Mehran (1992) reported a positive and statistically significant relationship between ownership by largest individual investors and short-term debt ratio; however, the relationship is insignificant with long-term debt ratio.

2.4 Managerial ownership

Agency problems between managers and shareholders may arise because managers have a tendency to consume more than optimal level of perks, and invest resources at blow the cost of capital or wasting it on organization inefficiencies. Although managers receive the full benefits of these activities but bear less than their share of full costs. Jensen and Meckling (1976) argued that as manager ownership of the firm's stock increases, the interests of manager and outside shareholders become more closely aligned. Thus, agency costs of equity may be reduced by increasing the proportion of managerial ownership in the firm. In an empirical study on listed firms in NYSE, Friend and Lang (1988) found that ownership of managerial insiders is negatively related to the debt ratio in closely held corporations with and without non-managerial principal shareholders. Furthermore, the management's shareholding is negatively related to debt ratio only in publicly held corporations with non-managerial principal shareholders but is less significant compared to closely held corporations, reflecting a lesser desire and ability of management in publicly held corporations to adjust debt ratio by their own interests. Alternatively, the agency literature also suggests that firms may use debt to minimize the agency problems between shareholders and managers. Grossman and Hart (1982) suggest that the use of debt force the managers to consume fewer perquisites and become more efficient to reduce the probability of bankruptcy and the loss of control. Jensen (1986) suggests that debt servicing commitments reduce the management's discretionary control over the firm's free cash flow that would otherwise be invested in low-return projects. Thus, these explanations suggest that both managerial ownership and debt provides support to align the interests of outside shareholders with management.

Findings are mixed on the relationship between managerial ownership and capital structure. Berger et al. (1997) have shown a positive and significant relationship between leverage and CEO's direct stock ownership suggesting that managers whose financial incentives are more closely aligned with outside shareholders will pursue more levered capital structure to increase the value of the firm. Mehran (1992) reported a positive and statistically significant relationship between managerial ownership and leverage suggesting that share ownership gives managers an incentive to increase the firm's leverage. Kim and Sorensen (1986) found that firms with higher insider ownership have greater debt ratios compared to firms with lower insider ownership. Wiwattanakantang (1999) found no significant relationship between CEOs and directors' ownership and debt-equity choice. Bokpin and Arko (2009) reported a positive and significant relationship between inside ownership and capital structure. Alternatively, Fosberg found a negative association between capital structure and shares held by the CEO suggesting that CEO will put their personal interests ahead than those of shareholders. Bathala et al. (1994) reported a negative association between debt ratio and managerial ownership suggesting that firms trade-off managerial ownership and debt in order to control the agency costs of the firm.

2.5 Director remuneration

The agency theory focuses on the issue of agency costs that arise due to divergence in interests between managers and outside shareholders. Efforts to force managers to act in the shareholder's interest could result in monitoring costs which are in some situations become so large as to make such exact compliance unattractive. Moreover, complexities in monitoring the management behavior result in establishment of organizational mechanisms that may achieve compliance in a gainful way. One such mechanism is to introduce a compensation package which motivates the managers to choose those actions that increase the shareholder's wealth. For instance, Jensen and Murphy (1990) estimated the pay-performance relationship for CEO and found that pay-performance sensitivity is statistically significant; however, the magnitude seems small in terms of the implied incentives because CEO wealth changes \$3.25 only for every \$1,000 change in the shareholder's wealth. Main (1991) found a positive and statistically significant relationship between top executive pay and returns to shareholders. In another study Main et al. (1996) found a significant and positive association between board remuneration and company performance. Conversely, Abdullah (2006) found a significant negative relationship between return on assets and director remuneration in Malaysian distressed firms. John and John (1993) studied the inter-relationship between top management compensation and design and the mix of external claims issued by the firms. They found a negative association between pay performance sensitivity and leverage. Wen et al. (2002) reported a negative relationship between CEO compensation and capital structure; however, the relationship is statistically insignificant.

2.6 CEO duality

Generally CEO has the executive responsibility to manage the firm's business; whereas, the chairman has the responsibility to handle the affairs of the board. CEO duality exists when a firm's CEO also serve as chairman in the board of directors. In particular, duality offers the clear direction of a single leader along with a faster response to external events. Furthermore, duality increases the discretion of CEO by providing a broader power base and locus of control (Boyd, 1995). The agency theory suggests that conflicts between shareholders and management can be reduced by separating the tasks of decision management and decision control. Thus, CEO has the primary responsibility for initiating and implementing the strategic decisions (decision management) while board has the responsibility for endorsing and monitoring the decisions of CEO (decision control). However, delegating both tasks to CEO might weaken the board control and negatively affect the firm performance. Alternatively, the stewardship and resource dependence theory suggests that CEO duality would facilitate effective action by the CEO, and therefore lead to high performance. Pfeffer and Salanick (1978) argued that leaders with greater discretion would be better able to implement their strategic decisions, and more likely to overcome organizational indolence. Brickley et al. (1997) argued that there is no single optimal leadership structure because both duality and separation perspectives have related costs and benefits. Thus, duality will be beneficial for some firms while separation is likely be valuable for others.

A few studies have analyzed the relationship between CEO duality and capital structure; however, empirical findings yields mixed results. Fosberg (2004) in his study on US corporations found that dual leadership structure is effective in increasing the amount of debt in a firm's capital structure; however, the relationship is less significant. Kyereboah-Coleman and Biekpe (2006) found a negative and significant association between CEO duality and the short-term leverage and the total leverage suggesting that when CEO also serves as chairperson of the board, agency cost rise and this factor discourage the lenders to invest in such entities. They also reported a positive association between CEO duality and long-term leverage but the relationship is statistically insignificant. Abor (2007) found a significant and positive relationship between CEO duality and leverage. Bokpin and Arko (2009) reported a positive but statistically insignificant relationship between CEO duality and financial leverage suggesting that an entrenched CEO prefer to finance the firm's operations by using debt capital rather issuing new equity.

3. Methodology

This paper examines the corporate governance attributes that may affect the capital structure of non-financial services firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) during 2012-2021. The data were obtained from the yearly annual reports of companies included in the sample. In particular, an annual report is a collection of financial and non-financial reports such as a balance sheet, an income statement, a cash flow statement, a

statement of changes in owner equity, an auditor report, a pattern of shareholding, and general information about the company's directors, chairman, and chief executive officer. Initially all 75 non-financial firms were included in the sample. The total observations amount to 750, which is 750 firms over a period of ten years. This study uses two measures of capital structure as dependent variables i.e. the total debt ratio and the long-term debt ratio. The explanatory variables include board size, outside directors, ownership concentration, managerial ownership, director remuneration, and CEO duality. In addition to these corporate governance variables, we have included in our model standard control variables for other firm's attributes that may affect the capital structure. Control variables include the firm's profitability, size, liquidity, and asset tangibility. Definitions of these variables are listed in Table I. Furthermore, definitions of variables are largely adopted from existing literature with the aim of making a meaningful comparison with earlier empirical studies. All variables are measured using book values because the data comes from annual reports only.

3. Methodology

This study employed panel data methodology because sample contained data across firms and over time. Moreover, panel data sets are better able to identify and estimate effects that simply are not detectable in pure cross-sections or pure time series data. The basic regression model is specified as follows:

$$CS_{i,t} = P_0 + P_1BS_{i,t} + P_2OD_{i,t} + P_3OC_{i,t} + P_4MO_{i,t} + P_5DREM_{i,t} + P_6CD_{i,t} + P_7PROF_{i,t} + P_8SIZE_{i,t} + P_9LIQ_{i,t} + P_{10}AT_{i,t} + e_{i,t}$$

Therefore,

$$TDR_{i,t} = P_0 + P_1BS_{i,t} + P_2OD_{i,t} + P_3OC_{i,t} + P_4MO_{i,t} + P_5DREM_{i,t} + P_6CD_{i,t} + P_7PROF_{i,t} + P_8SIZE_{i,t} + P_9LIQ_{i,t} + P_{10}AT_{i,t} + e_{i,t}$$

$$LTDR_{i,t} = P_0 + P_1BS_{i,t} + P_2OD_{i,t} + P_3OC_{i,t} + P_4MO_{i,t} + P_5DREM_{i,t} + P_6CD_{i,t} + P_7PROF_{i,t} + P_8SIZE_{i,t} + P_9LIQ_{i,t} + P_{10}AT_{i,t} + e_{i,t}$$

whereas i denotes the cross-section script, t indicates the time script, $CS_{i,t}$ is the firm i 's capital structure at time t , explanatory variables are $BS_{i,t}$, $OD_{i,t}$, $OC_{i,t}$, $MOWN_{i,t}$, $DREM_{i,t}$, $CD_{i,t}$, $PROF_{i,t}$, $SIZE_{i,t}$, $LIQ_{i,t}$, and $AT_{i,t}$ for the i th firm in the t th period, P is a vector of parameters, $e_{i,t}$ is a disturbance term. Table 1 shows the variables and their meaning.

Table 1. Definition of Variables

Variables	Definition
<i>Dependent variables</i>	
Total debt ratio (TDR_{it})	Ratio of total debt to total assets. Total debt is the sum of short-term debt and long-term debt
Long-term debt ratio ($LTDR_{it}$)	Ratio of long-term debt to total assets
<i>Explanatory variables</i>	
Board size (BS_{it})	Logarithm of number of board members
Outside directors (OD_{it})	Ratio of outside directors to total board members
Ownership concentration (OC_{it})	Ratio of shares held by five largest shareholders to total outstanding shares
Managerial ownership ($MOWN_{it}$)	Ratio of shares held by CEOs, directors, and their immediate family members to total outstanding shares
Director remuneration ($DREM_{it}$)	Logarithm of director remuneration
CEO duality (CD_{it})	A dummy variable, 1 if CEO is the Chairman, 0 otherwise
<i>Control variables</i>	
Profitability ($PROF_{it}$)	Ratio net profit after taxes to total assets
Size ($SIZE_{it}$)	Natural logarithm of total assets
Liquidity (LIQ_{it})	Ratio of current assets to current liabilities
Asset tangibility (AT_{it})	Ratio of net fixed assets to total assets

where $TDR_{i,t}$ is total debt ratio of firm i at time t , $LTDR_{i,t}$ is long-term debt ratio of firm i at time t , $BS_{i,t}$ is board size of firm i at time t , $OD_{i,t}$ is non-executive/outside directors of firm i at time t , $OC_{i,t}$ is ownership concentration of firm i at time t , $MOWN_{i,t}$ is managerial ownership of firm i at time t , $DREM_{i,t}$ is director remuneration of firm i at time t , $CD_{i,t}$ is CEO duality of firm i at time t , $PROF_{i,t}$ is profitability of firm i at time t , $SIZE_{i,t}$ is size of firm i at time t , $LIQ_{i,t}$ is liquidity of firm i at time t , $AT_{i,t}$ is asset tangibility of firm i at time t , P_0 is common intercept, P_{1-10} are the coefficients of explanatory variables, and $e_{i,t}$ is error term of firm i at time t .

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of dependent and explanatory variables used in this study. In particular, the average total debt ratio and long-term debt ratio for the sample of firms is 59.62 percent and 22.23 percent. The average total debt ratio, in comparison with firms in other countries indicate that Nigerian firms tend to use more debt in their capital structure compared to firms in other countries. The average long-term debt ratio shows that Nigerian firms tend to have less long-term liabilities compared to firms in other countries. The results substantiate the findings of Demirguc-Kunt and Maksimovic (1999) that firms in developing countries generally hold lower amounts of long-term debt. The mean of outside directors is about 7 percent indicating a very low representation of independent directors in the firms' boards compared to large US public corporations (53.90 percent) reported by Berger et al. (1997). On average approximately in 25 percent of the cases the CEO also serves as the chairman of the board. The managerial ownership is about 30 percent and the share ownership by five largest individuals is about 58 percent.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Obs	Mean	Std dev	Minimum	Maximum
TDR_{it}	750	0.59624	0.192	0.04541	0.99394
$LTDR_{it}$	750	0.22231	0.167	0.00000	0.87651
BS_{it}	750	0.89424	0.069	0.84509	1.14612
OD_{it}	750	0.06837	0.104	0.00000	0.60000
OC_{it}	750	0.58362	0.182	0.06200	0.97342
$MOWN_{it}$	750	0.29658	0.247	5.35e-09	0.96595
$DREM_{it}$	750	6.61306	0.54402	3.99246	7.90469
CD_{it}	750	0.24903	0.43273	0.00000	1.00000
$PROF_{it}$	750	0.06600	0.10699	20.31727	0.79671
$SIZE_{it}$	750	21.4830	1.38317	17.91891	25.5683
LIQ_{it}	750	1.41727	1.06995	0.126257	11.7963
AT_{it}	750	0.54661	0.19533	0.026127	0.95639

Source: STATA 14 Outputs

Table 3. Yearly mean value of shareholding pattern

% Shares	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	mean
CEOs	4.08	4.09	4.82	4.08	4.09	4.82	4.08	4.09	4.82	4.08	3.73
Directors	8.46	8.76	8.55	8.46	8.76	8.55	8.46	8.76	8.55	8.46	8.18
Directors	1.38	1.36	1.20	1.38	1.36	1.20	1.38	1.36	1.20	1.38	1.37
Total	13.92	14.21	14.57	13.92	14.21	14.57	13.92	14.21	14.57	13.92	13.28
Banks	6.60	6.77	8.60	6.60	6.77	8.60	6.60	6.77	8.60	6.60	7.82
Insurance companies	2.06	1.96	1.85	2.06	1.96	1.85	2.06	1.96	1.85	2.06	1.96
Registrars	1.17	1.15	1.25	1.17	1.15	1.25	1.17	1.15	1.25	1.17	1.08
Investment companies	3.94	3.75	3.50	3.94	3.75	3.50	3.94	3.75	3.50	3.94	3.90
Total	13.77	13.63	15.20	13.77	13.63	15.20	13.77	13.63	15.20	13.77	14.76
Other companies	42.51	43.21	42.85	42.51	43.21	42.85	42.51	43.21	42.85	42.51	42.79
General public	29.80	28.95	27.38	29.80	28.95	27.38	29.80	28.95	27.38	29.80	29.17
Grand total	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Table 3 presents the general picture of the ownership structure of non-financial firms included in our sample. The largest shareholders of Nigeria listed firms are the other companies which hold on average 42.79 percent outstanding shares. General public emerge as the second largest shareholder holding on average 29.17 percent of total outstanding shares. Shares held by financial institutions are relatively low. Banks, insurance companies, registrars, and investment companies together hold on average 14.76 percent of the total outstanding shares. Finally, shares held by the CEOs, directors, and their immediate family members amounts to 13.28 percent.

4.2 Correlation matrix

Before estimating the coefficients the data was tested for multicollinearity. Table 4 presents the pair-wise correlation matrix for all variables used in the model. The correlation matrix does not suggest any serious concern for multicollinearity problems.

Table 4 Correlation matrix for variables used in model

Variable	TDR MOWN	LTDR DREM	BS	OD	OC	CD	PROF	SIZE	LIQ	AT
TDR	1									
LTDR	0.60***	1								
BS	0.04	0.06*	1							
OD	0.11***	0.07**	0.13***	1						
OC	20.1***	20.06*	20.01	20.0**	1					
MOWN	0.14***	0.09***	20.1***	20.0**	20.001	1				
DREM	20.3***	20.2***	0.26***	0.008	0.21***					
CD	20.3***	1								
	0.06*	0.08**	20.08**	0.033	20.028					
	0.23***	20.0***				1				
PROF	20.5***	20.3***	0.12***	20.057	0.18***	20.1**	1			
	20.2***	0.38***	SIZE	0.003		*	0.16**	1		
	0.070*	0.39***		0.068*	0.12***		*	20.04	1	
	20.3***	0.43***				20.04	*	20.04	0	20.3
LIQ	20.6***	20.3***	20.018	20.0**	0.14***	2	0.4***	0	20.3	1
	20.2***	0.23***	AT	0.14***	0.69***	20.1**	20.37*	0.07***	***	
	20.024	0.023	20.08**	0.15***	20.1***	*	*			
										0.16***

Notes: * ¼ Significant at 10 percent level; ** ¼ Significant at 5 percent level; *** ¼ Significant at 1 percent level

4.3 Regression results

The estimation results are presented in Tables 5 and 6 indicate that coefficients of board size, outside directors, and ownership concentration are statistically significant and positively related to the total debt ratio and the long-term debt ratio. The coefficients of director remuneration are statistically significant and negatively related to the total debt ratio and the long-term debt ratio. The coefficients of managerial ownership are negatively related to the total debt ratio and the long-term debt ratio; however, the relationship is significant only with the long-term debt ratio. The coefficients of CEO duality found to highly insignificant with negative signs in all regressions. The coefficients of control variables in the regression such as profitability and liquidity are statistically significant and negatively related to the total debt ratio and the long-term debt ratio. The coefficients of the firm’s size are statistically significant and positively related to the total debt ratio and the long-term debt ratio. The coefficients of asset tangibility are statistically significant and positively related to the long-term debt ratio, while negatively related to the total debt ratio. The OLS regressions have high adjusted R² and appear to be able to explicate variations in the capital structure. Moreover, the F-statistic confirms the significance of the estimation model.

Table 5. Regression Results for Model 1

Variable (TDR)	Coefficient	Std. error	t-statistic	Prob.
C	0.857060	0.092100	9.31	0.000
BS _{it}	0.193356	0.072663	2.66	0.008
OD _{it}	0.110904	0.044569	2.49	0.013
OC _{it}	0.054968	0.025892	2.12	0.034
MOWN _{it}	20.027881	0.020906	21.33	0.183
DREM _{it}	20.065178	0.009992	26.52	0.000
CD _{it}	20.004538	0.010879	20.42	0.677
PROF _{it}	20.584529	0.051772	211.29	0.000
SIZE _{it}	0.011384	0.004118	2.76	0.006
LIQ _{it}	20.100180	0.004957	220.21	0.000
AT _{it}	20.177427	0.025982	26.83	0.000

Notes: R² 0.5761; Mean dependent var 0.5962; Adjusted R² 0.5706; Std. error of regression 0.1255; F-statistic 103.83; Prob. - F-statistic 0.0000.

Table 6. Regression Results for Model 1

Variable (LTDR)	Coefficient	Std. error	t-statistic	Prob.
C	20.037374	0.083846	20.45	0.656
BS _{it}	0.233208	0.066151	3.53	0.000
OD _{it}	0.073574	0.040575	1.81	0.070
OC _{it}	0.040435	0.023572	1.72	0.087
MOWN _{it}	20.039714	0.019032	22.09	0.037
DREM _{it}	20.055951	0.009097	26.15	0.000
CD _{it}	20.009483	0.009904	20.96	0.339
PROF _{it}	20.163532	0.047132	23.47	0.001
SIZE _{it}	0.006486	0.003749	1.73	0.084
LIQ _{it}	20.010136	0.003749	22.25	0.025
AT _{it}	0.535059	0.023654	22.62	0.000

Notes: R² 0.5404; Mean dependent var. 0.2223; Adjusted R² 0.5344; Std. error of regression 0.1142; F-statistic 89.82; Prob. - F-statistic 0.0000.

4.4 Discussion

The board size is statistically significant and positively related to the total debt ratio and the long-term debt ratio. This finding is consistent with the resource dependence theory suggesting that firms with large boards have more ability to raise funds from external sources in order to enhance the value of the firm. Therefore, results may reflect the nature of the environment in which Nigeria firms operate whereby large boards serve as

a means of obtaining support from the environment. Moreover, commercial banks and development financial institutions also feel confident while extending loans to firms with large size boards. The positive relationship of board size with capital structure is consistent with other studies including Abor (2007), Anderson et al. (2004), Bokpin and Arko (2009), and Kyereboah-Coleman and Biekpe (2006). The results show that coefficients of outside directors are statistically significant and positively related to the total debt ratio and the long-term debt ratio. This finding suggests that a board with more independent directors can monitor the management more actively, and therefore force the management to choose those actions that maximize the shareholder wealth. Moreover, the presence of independent directors on the firm's board improves the creditability which make possible for the firm to borrow more on favorable terms to avail the tax shields benefit. In general, commercial banks and development financial institutions are the main suppliers of funds to firms in Nigeria because of undeveloped and limited bond market. Moreover, these banks find it advantageous to extend loans on favourable terms to firms with more independent directors because of effective monitoring. The positive relationship between outside directors and capital structure is consistent with earlier studies including Abor (2007), Anderson et al. (2004), Berger et al. (1997), and Pfeffer (1972).

The ownership concentration is statistically significant and positively related to the total debt ratio and the long-term debt ratio. This finding suggests that blockholders have more ability than dispersed shareholders to force the management to take on more debt in order to reduce managerial opportunism, apart from tax shields considerations. Descriptive statistics shown in Table II indicates that ownership concentration is very high among Nigeria firms because five individuals hold a significant (58.36 percent) proportion of total shares issued by the firms. The positive relationship between ownership concentration and capital structure is consistent with the findings of Berger et al. (1997), Brailsford et al. (2002), Fosberg (2004), and Mehran (1992). The managerial ownership is negatively related to the total debt ratio and the long term debt ratio; however, the relationship is statistically significant with the long-term debt ratio. This finding is consistent with the agency theory suggesting that increased managerial ownership aligns the interests of managers with outside shareholders and reduces the role of debt as a tool to mitigate the agency conflicts. Moreover, this finding confirms that high leverage is less attractive to managers because it imposes higher risk to managers than to public investors. The negative relationship between managerial ownership and capital structure is consistent with the findings of Bathala et al. (1994), Friend and Lang (1988), and Fosberg (2004).

Director remuneration is statistically significant and negatively related to the total debt ratio and the long-term debt ratio. This finding suggests that directors pursue lower leverage to avoid extra risk and pressures associated with the use of high leverage and to keep their positions intact for good salary and bonuses. Finally, the variable CEO duality is negatively related to the total debt ratio and the long-term debt ratio but the relationship is statistically insignificant. The negative relationship indicates that when CEO also serves as chairman in the board, he prefer to use less debt in order to avoid the extra pressure and risk associated with the employability of high leverage. The negative relationship between CEO duality and capital structure is consistent with the of Berger et al. (1997) showing that leverage is significantly lower in firms where CEO does not appear to face strong monitoring. The control variables included in estimation model have sings in line with widely acknowledged models of capital structure. The negative and significant relationships of profitability and liquidity with leverage are consistent with the pecking order hypothesis showing that firms with high profits and more liquid resources tend to borrow less than firms with low profits and less liquid resources. The positive relationship between firm size and leverage is consistent with the static trade-off model suggesting that large firms should borrow more due to their ability to diversify the risk and to avail the benefit of tax shields on interest payments. The results show that asset tangibility is positively related to the long-term debt ratio and negatively related to the total debt ratio. Similar relationship is observed by Booth et al. (2001) for Nigeria firms included in their sample which substantiate the estimation of this study. Bokpin and Arko (2009) have also reported a significant negative relationship between total debt ratio and asset tangibility for Ghanaian firms. The positive relationship between asset tangibility and long-term leverage is consistent with the predictions of the static trade-off model which postulates that firms with more collateralizable assets tend to borrow more than firms with risky intangible assets. Moreover, issuing debt secured by collateralizable assets may protect the debtholders from the opportunistic behavior of managers because it restricts the borrower to use funds for a specified project. The negative relationship between asset tangibility and total debt ratio is in contradiction with theoretical prediction. The reason for this result would need some theoretical support, which is not provided by this study.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This empirical study attempted to investigate the effects of corporate governance on capital structure of non-financial services firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group during 2012-2021. Empirical results indicate that board size, outside directors, and ownership concentration are positively related with both measures of capital structure (i.e. the total debt ratio and the long-term debt ratio). Managerial ownership is negatively related to the long-term debt ratio. Director remuneration is negatively related with both measures of capital structure. CEO duality is also negatively related with both measures of capital structure; however, the relationship is statistically insignificant. The positive relationship between board size and capital structure is consistent with the resource dependence theory suggesting that a large board serve as a means to obtain support from external environment. The positive relationship between outside directors and capital structure indicate that boards with more independent directors can take on more debt on favorable terms due to effective monitoring. The positive relationship between ownership concentration and capital structure indicates that blockholders are the effective monitors and have more ability than dispersed shareholders to force management to take those actions (i.e. use of optimal level of debt than personally desired by the managers) that maximize the shareholder wealth. The negative relationship between managerial ownership and capital structure indicates that increased managerial ownership aligns the interests of managers with the interests of outside shareholders and reduces the role of debt as a tool to mitigate the agency problems. The negative relationship between director remuneration and capital structure shows that directors attempt to use less debt in order to avoid extra pressure and risk associated with high leverage, and to keep their positions intact for good salary and bonuses. The negative relationship of profitability and liquidity with capital structure is consistent with the pecking order hypothesis showing that firms with high profit and more liquid resources tend to borrow less than firms with low profits. The positive relationship of size with capital structure is consistent with the static trade-off model suggesting that large firms should borrow more due to their ability to diversify the risk. Finally, the positive relationship between asset tangibility and long-term debt ratio suggest that firms with more collateralizable asset tend to borrow more than firms with risky intangible assets. In summary, despite the significant steps taken by the government of Nigeria to improve the level of corporate governance in the country, Nigeria firms still have weak internal and external corporate governance mechanisms compared to firms in developed countries. However, the results indicate that corporate governance attributes, in part, explicate the financing behavior of Nigeria firms. Moreover, this study has laid some groundwork by illuminating the significant links between corporate governance measures and capital structure on which a more detailed evaluation could be based.

References

- Abdullah, S. N. (2006). Directors' remuneration, firm's performance and corporate governance in Malaysia among distressed firms", *Corporate Governance*, 6(2), 162-74.
- Abor, J. (2007), "Corporate governance and financing decisions of Ghanaian listed firms", *Corporate Governance*, Vol. 7 No. 1, pp. 83-92.
- Adams, R. and Mehran, H. (2003), "Is corporate governance different for bank holding companies?", *Federal Reserve Bank of New York Economic Policy Review*, pp. 123-42.
- Anderson, R.C., Mansi, S.A. and Reeb, D.M. (2004), "Board characteristics, accounting report integrity, and the cost of debt", *Journal of Accounting and Economics*, Vol. 37, pp. 315-42.
- Bathala, C.T., Moon, K.P. and Rao, R.P. (1994), "Managerial ownership, debt policy, and the impact of institutional holdings: an agency perspective", *Financial Management*, Vol. 23 No. 3, pp. 38-50.
- Berger, P.G., Ofek, E. and Yermack, D.L. (1997), "Managerial entrenchment and capital structure decisions", *The Journal of Finance*, Vol. LII No. 4, pp. 1411-38.
- Bokpin, G.A. and Arko, A.C. (2009), "Ownership structure, corporate governance, and capital structure decisions of firms: empirical evidence from Ghana", *Studies in Economics and Finance*, 26(4), 246-56.
- Booth, L., Aivazian, V., Demircug-Kunt, A. and Maksimovic, V. (2001), "Capital structures in developing countries", *The Journal of Finance*, Vol. 56 No. 1, pp. 87-130.
- Boyd, B.K. (1995), "CEO duality and firm performance: a contingency model", *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 16 No. 4, pp. 301-12.
- Brailsford, T.J., Oliver, B.R. and Pua, S.L.H. (2002), "On the relation between ownership structure and capital structure", *Accounting and Finance*, Vol. 42, pp. 1-26.

- Brickley, J., Coles, J. and Jarrell, G. (1997), "Leadership structure: separating the CEO and chairman of the board", *Journal of Corporate Finance*, Vol. 3, pp. 189-220.
- Demirguc-Kunt, A. and Maksimovic, V. (1999), "Institutions, financial markets and firm debt maturity", *Journal of Financial Economics*, Vol. 54, pp. 295-336.
- Fosberg, R.H. (2004), "Agency problems and debt financing: leadership structure effects", *Corporate Governance*, Vol. 4 No. 1, pp. 31-48.
- Friend, I. and Lang, L.H.P. (1988), "An empirical test of the impact of managerial self-interest on corporate capital structure", *The Journal of Finance*, Vol. 43 No. 2, pp. 271-81.
- Grossman, S.J. and Hart, O. (1982), "Corporate financial structure and managerial incentives", in McCall, J. (Ed.), *The Economics of Information and Uncertainty*, University of Chicago Press, Chicago, IL.
- Jensen, M.C. (1986), "Agency costs of free cash flow, corporate finance, and takeovers", *The American Economic Review*, Vol. 76 No. 2, pp. 323-9.
- Jensen, M.C. and Meckling, W.H. (1976), "Theory of the firm: managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure", *Journal of Financial Economics*, Vol. 3 No. 40, pp. 305-60.
- Jensen, M.C. and Murphy, K.J. (1990), "Performance pay and top management incentives", *The Journal of Political Economy*, Vol. 98 No. 2, pp. 225-64.
- John, T.A. and John, K. (1993), "Top management compensation and capital structure", *The Journal of Finance*, Vol. 48 No. 3, pp. 949-74.
- Kim, W.H. and Sorensen, E.H. (1986), "Evidence on the impact of the agency costs of debt on corporate debt policy", *The Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, Vol. 21 No. 2, pp. 131-44.
- Kyereboah-Coleman, A. and Biekpe, N. (2006), "Corporate governance and financing choices of firms: a panel data analysis", *South African Journal of Economics*, Vol. 74 No. 4, pp. 670-81.
- Lipton, M. and Lorsch, J. (1992), "A modest proposal for improved corporate governance", *Business Lawyer*, 48, pp. 59-77.
- Main, B.G.M. (1991), "Top executive pay and performance", *Managerial and Decision Economics*, 12(3), 219-29.
- Main, B.G.M., Bruce, A. and Buck, T. (1996), "The board remuneration and company performance", *The Economic Journal*, Vol. 106 No. 439, pp. 1627-44.
- Mehran, H. (1992), "Executive incentive plans, corporate control, and capital structure", *The Journal of Financial and Quantitative Analysis*, Vol. 27 No. 4, pp. 539-60.
- Pfeffer, J. (1972), "Size and composition of corporate boards of directors: the organization and its environment", *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 17 No. 2, pp. 218-28.
- Pfeffer, J. and Salanick, G.R. (1978), *The External Control of Organizations: A Resource Dependence Perspective*, Harper & Row, New York, NY.
- Rajan, R.G. and Zingales, L. (1995), "What do we know about capital structure? Some evidence from international data", *The Journal of Finance*, Vol. 50 No. 5, pp. 1421-60.
- Shleifer, A. and Vishny, R.W. (1997), "A survey of corporate governance", *The Journal of Finance*, 52(2), 737-83.
- Weisbach, M. (1988), "Outside directors and CEO turnover", *Journal of Financial Economics*, Vol. 20, pp. 431-60.
- Wen, Y., Rwegasira, K. and Bilderbeek, J. (2002), "Corporate governance and capital structure decisions of the Chinese listed firms", *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, Vol. 10 No. 2, pp. 75-83.
- Wiwattanakitang, Y. (1999), "An empirical study on the determinants of the capital structure of Thai firms", *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, Vol. 7, pp. 371-403.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2006). Empirical evidence on the effect of size on the profitability of Nigerian commercial banks. *Journal of Social Studies*, 11(4), 33-39.
- Yahaya, O. A. (2019). Intellectual capital management and financial competitiveness of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *Enugu State University J. of Management Sciences*, 12(1), 86-96.
- Yahaya, O. A., & Andow, H. A. (2015). Capital structure and firm's financial performance: Panel evidence of listed conglomerate firms in Nigeria. *Kaduna Business Management Review*, 2(1), 45-56.
- Yahaya, O. A., Tanko, M., & Liman, M. L. (2017). Effects of corporate characteristics on earnings quality of listed deposit money banks in Nigeria. *Kaduna State University Journal of Management Sciences*, 8(1), 47-64.
- Yahaya, O. A., Tijani, B. (2020). Internal corporate governance and intellectual capital of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Review*, 8(9), 98-112.
- Yahaya, O. A., Awon, B. I. (2021). Chief executive officers and bankruptcy of quoted resources companies in

Nigeria. *Fountain Journal of Management Sciences*, 10(2), 970-980.

Yahaya, O. A., Tijjani, B. (2021). Size, age and leverage of Nigeria quoted oil and gas corporations. *Advanced Int. Journal of Banking, Accounting and Finance*, 3(6), 51-60.

Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEOs influence earnings management? *South African Journal of Accounting Research*, 36(2), 1-13.

Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does CEO characteristics affect dividend policy? *Review of Accounting Studies*, 27(2), 375-389.

Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. G. (2022). The board of directors' influence on the intellectual capital of Nigeria listed firms. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 37(2), 1-17.

Yahaya, O. A., Onyabe, J. M., Yusuf, M. J., & Tijjani, B. (2019). Financial mix and financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Management*, 2(1), 226-237.

Yahaya, O. A., & Apochi, J. (2021). Board of directors and corporate social responsibility reporting of quoted companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting, Finance and Auditing Studies*, 7(2), 38-52.

Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Board characteristics and profitability. *Financial Markets, Institutions and Risks*, 6(3), 115-130.

Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Corporate governance and profitability: An application of Agency Theory. *Journal of Accounting Research*, 34(2), 406-421.

Yahaya, O. A., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Does board of directors improve profitability? *Accounting*, 8(2022), 269-275.

Yahaya, O. A., & Abdulfatah, L. A. (2022). Can auditors reduce earnings management activities? *Review of Accounting and Finance*, 22(4), 429-442.

Yahaya, O. A., Mohammed, I., Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Board governance and sustainability disclosure of Nigeria listed deposit money banks. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 10(5), 126-147.

Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Chief executive officer and firm value: Evidence from Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *Journal of Economic and Financial Studies* (ISSN 2379-9463(Print), ISSN 2379-9471(Online), 10(3), 12-21.

Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Remuneration committee and profitability: Evidence from Nigeria. *Dinasti International Journal of Economics, Finance and Accounting* (e-ISSN: 2721-303X, p-ISSN: 2721-3021), 4(3), 220-231.

Yahaya, O. A., & Yakubu, I. (2022). Risk committee's influence on enterprise risk management. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 15(4): 120, 1-15.

Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does Board Gender Diversity Influence Dividend Pay-Out? Evidence from Nigeria Non-Financial Services Sector. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance and Risk Management*, 7(2), 25-33.

Itopa, E., Alexander, S., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Board of directors and earnings management: Evidence from the Nigerian Exchange Group. *Journal of Accounting and Finance* (ISSN: 2158-3625), 22(3), 45-59.

Apochi, J. G., Mohammed, S. G., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Ownership structure, board of directors and financial performance: Evidence in Nigeria. *Global Review of Accounting and Finance* (ISSN: 1838-1413 Paper, ISSN 1838-5915 Online), 13(1), 77-98.

Awen, B. I., Adewinmisi, G. O., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). The influence of ownership structure on dividend policy in reducing agency problems in Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *International Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 12(3), 99-111.

Tijjani, B., & Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Does corporate governance improve energy information disclosure among Nigeria listed manufacturing firms? *Journal of Advanced Research in Business and Management Studies* (ISSN: 2462-1935), 26(3), 15-26.

Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Chief executive officer and firm value: Evidence from Nigeria listed non-financial services companies. *Journal of Economic and Financial Studies* (ISSN 2379-9463(Print), ISSN 2379-9471(Online), 10(3), 12-21.

Yahaya, O. A., & Awen, B. I. (2022). Does ownership structure lead to optimal financial structure? *Seisense Journal of Management* (ISSN: 2617-5770-Online), 5(4), 51-64.

Yahaya, O. A. (2022). Board characteristics and profitability. *Financial Markets, Institutions and Risks* (ISSN (print) – 2521-1250, ISSN (online) – 2521-1242), 6(3), 115-130.

Yahaya, O. A., & Mohammed, S. G. (2022). Does board of directors improve profitability? *Accounting* (ISSN 2369-7407 (Online) - ISSN 2369-7393 (Print)), 8(2022), 269-275.